

IMPACT OF TECHNOLOGY ON EDUCATION**Rakhimova Zarina Uktamovna**

Scientific supervisor.

The teacher of “History and Philology” department of Asia International University

Marufova Dilnoza Raufjonovna

Student.

The student of Asia International University

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Abstract. *This article provides an overview of technological advancements and how they have altered society, particularly in the field of education. The greatest human innovation that has altered every aspect of our daily life is without a doubt technology. The use of technology in the classroom has increased over time, particularly since the COVID-19 epidemic. Like anything else in this world, technology has advantages and disadvantages. This article briefly discusses both the advantages and disadvantages of technology in the classroom.*

Key words: *Worldwide, fraudulent activities, shortcut, apathetic, burden, extracurricular.*

Introduction: Everywhere we look, we can see how technology has taken over the globe and every industry. One of the main achievements of technology that has completely changed our life is the computer. Many sectors evolved alongside technologies, gradually integrating technology into their work practices. Technology was progressively used in more sectors of the economy, including healthcare, finance, food service, and education, to the point that these sectors could not function without it. An economy can no longer expand in a nation with inadequate technology. For a very long time, traditional in-class instruction has been the most successful method of learning. Prior to the Covid-19 outbreak stopping meetings in, this approach was the most popular and effective.

Main part: Literature review: Using contemporary technological equipment has improved student learning and interactivity, according to the most recent research on the effects of technology on contemporary students. Our interests have always been higher when technology is involved than when traditional methods are used, and this is especially true in the educational setting. Furthermore, the internet represents the very beginning of technology in education; before to the discovery of the internet, computers were merely tools. Only then did they attain their full potential.

Over the years, its requirements and significance have increased to the point where a minute-long internet outage has significant worldwide effects. Teachers and students can benefit much from the internet, despite its reputation for negative aspects and fraudulent activities.

First of all writing abilities have significantly decreased since many students now would rather use laptops in class than take notes. Additionally, because students practice typing shortcuts when speaking online and on social media, they also tend to use these shortcuts when writing, which has greatly improved their writing abilities. Students that rely too heavily on autocorrection are unable to spell words correctly, write in cursive, or utilize proper syntax. Students who use laptops in class have become apathetic and feel that writing is a burden. Additionally impacted severely are the youngsters' fine motor skills.

In addition technology improvement is leading to an increase in cheating as well. In an attempt to pass the tests, students discover new strategies and technologies. Technological innovations such as graphic calculators, smart watches, small cameras, and associated devices have evolved into powerful instruments for test fraud. Teachers may find it challenging to capture their students' attention in class when they are using technology, even though it might serve as a motivator for their learning. Because they are addicted to these things, they don't spend enough time studying at home, which affects their performance in school and occasionally even in extracurricular activities like sports.

Conclusion: In conclusion the great human innovation is very effective for the students and teachers. We can often see this invitation in the classroom where people can use for their need.

Particularly the COVID-19 epidemic was the cause to use it. Although COVID has slowed us back in time it has opened many possibilities in terms of education which was not possible previously. In general with article we wanted to discuss both negative and positive impact of technology with this way.

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